

A Higher Level of Education in Police Work is Essential to Improving Professional Development and Opportunities for Advancement

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Abstract:- This article seeks to determine whether police officers believe higher education is crucial to enhancing their professional development and chances for advancement. The dependent variable is the perceived level of higher education, which is assessed in three ways: the perceived value of a college degree, the perceived value of a criminal justice or criminology degree, and the perceived significance of particular career-related skills. Today, it is more typical for officers to hold official university degrees in an effort to modernize police organizations and professionalize policing. The professionalization of police forces in the United Kingdom has recently come under scrutiny (Tong, Hallenberg, and Simmill-Binning, Towers, 2017). The transition from conventional training programs to more formal higher education programs has therefore been recognized as a step forward in the development of professionalism within the police force (Paterson, 2011). Given recent advancements in the policing sector, modernization has taken center stage in efforts to prepare the workforce for the needs of the twenty-first century. Police studies discourse now includes discussion of the evolving complexity of police operations and the essence of policing (Ramshaw, Soppitt 2018).

Training and education of police officers is a crucial subject for police forces all over the world. The professionalization of policing has frequently been related to both education and training. Conflict resolution, leadership, and management abilities, as well as awareness of and regard for cultural diversity and human rights. These qualities should define a Serbian police officer in the twenty-first century. The list of these qualities is the result of a functional examination of the jobs that the future police are expected to perform. Given recent advancements in the policing sector, modernization has taken center stage in efforts to prepare the workforce for the needs of the twenty-first century. Police studies discourse has increasingly incorporated the evolving complexity of police work and the way it is done (Cordner, Shain, 2011).

Keywords:- Police Education, Professionalization and Professional Development. Policing Education Qualification Framework (PEQF),

I. INTRODUCTION

Thirty to forty years ago, the issue of police education was heavily disputed. At that time, there was a great deal of debate and critical inquiry in academic literature regarding the paths police education should go and the purposes it should serve. Since then, questions about police education such as what to teach officers, how to teach them, by whom, and within which conceptual or disciplinary framework have occasionally come up, but with less prominence and unquestionably less "fire" (see Cordner & Shain, Citation, 2011; Kratcoski, 2004; Haberfeld, 2002; Sherman, 1978). Numerous research studies and commissions of inquiry have focused on the importance of tertiary or higher education to policing in various parts of the world (Decker & Huckabee, 2002; Jones, Jones & Prenzler, 2005; Lee & Punch, 2004; Scaramella, Cox & McCamey, 2011). This does not imply that the importance of police postsecondary education has been effectively communicated and thoroughly ingrained into the practice of policing. However, it can be argued that some difficulties have had time to settle over the years and that the study of police education has undoubtedly aided policing scholarship and professional development.

Today, police education is once more at a crossroads. A number of jurisdictions throughout the world wish to face the issue head-on, and police education is re-emerging as a "hotspot" in modern policing. This is partially attributable to many movements that have come together to set standards for police education and professionalization. The demands for professionalization have grown in both police organizations and police education and training as a result of the police profession, like many other professions, becoming one that involves ever more varied and complex tasks in recent years (Filstad et al., 2020). To encourage more professionalization of police organizations, a series of educational reforms have been attempted, and in many countries, police education has been included into university systems as units or departments (Bjrgo and Damen, 2020). This progression is predicated on the idea that police officers working in a rapidly evolving and complex society need to supplement their police professional skills and that higher education that places a strong emphasis on theoretical knowledge can aid in the growth of a reflective and critical approach (Bringsrud Fekjaer et al., 2014). Assignments and professional approaches have been highlighted more frequently in recent years due to the growing need for professionalization in police education (Basham, 2014;

Shipton, 2019). To advance police education toward a more understanding- and communication-oriented and student-centered pedagogical teaching practice, Paterson (2011) highlights the need for increased theory and practice integration in police training professional development.

In order to carry out their tasks, police officers must adhere to many legal requirements as well as the requirements of the constitution. This type of work environment is characterized by this requirement. The social, cultural, historical, and political contexts in which police officers carry out their tasks are also expected of them. They are also expected to use their discretionary powers in a way that upholds the authority of the organization they represent and inspires public confidence. Police officials may find themselves unable to handle the constant pressure that is placed on them by the occupational environment in which they work due to the complexity of policing as well as the potential conflicts and demands inherent in police service. Some of these police officials may decide to pursue postgraduate studies for a variety of reasons, such as the expectation that obtaining such credentials will give them the knowledge and skills necessary to navigate the workplace environment or for the purpose of finding a suitable position within the organization.

Higher education curriculum value and appropriateness have long been the subject of academic discussion (Webb, 2006). In general, higher education has served two purposes: 1) a liberal education that emphasizes giving students a breadth of knowledge to help them become socially responsible citizens, and 2) a specialization of training for students to concentrate on a particular subject in depth (Axelrod, 2002). The relative weight of these two objectives has changed throughout time, and contemporary society seems to be placing more and more emphasis on the financial gains that students will experience after graduating (Filippakou & Williams, 2015). The relevance of some social science and humanities disciplines, however, may be in jeopardy if higher education is seen as nothing more than a vehicle for workforce development.

The need for and benefits of higher education for police personnel have long been debatable (Brown, 1974; Bruns & Magnan, 2014; Roberg & Bonn, 2004). Due to their greater exposure to diverse environments and cultures, college-educated police officers are thought to be better prepared than their high school-educated counterparts (Palmiotto, 1999; Rainford, 2016). This should improve their capacity for problem-solving and reduce their prejudice and bias. There is some evidence that exposure to higher education can promote police professionalism that is more mature and humanistic and that it can aid officers in improving their general communication abilities (Carlan & Byxbe, 2000; Carter & Sapp, 1990).

Increased educational requirements for entry-level jobs have been reluctant to follow calls for greater police education (Reaves, 2015). As college-educated officers may not be content with different parts of police employment,

critics have raised worry that raising the minimum educational level might have major effects on job satisfaction (Paoline et al., 2015). Furthermore, the educational prerequisite can reduce the applicant pool, perhaps rejecting many individuals who might otherwise be qualified (Bruns, and Schneider, 2016). For instance, Albarano (2015) made the point that a college education does not always work to combat negative views toward particular racial or ethnic groups or against particular crimes, nor does it always work to combat potential personality flaws that can have a detrimental effect on performance.

There is conflicting evidence in the literature on the usefulness of higher education regarding whether obtaining such credentials results in an improvement in performance (Cordner, 2014). According to Jones et al. (2005: 50), those who support police professionalism believe that higher education helps police officials become better at managing conflict and solving problems. Researchers like Braunstein and Paynich (2009) all hold the same opinion, arguing that police officers with a college degree behave more ethically, exhibit greater professionalism in their attitudes, and are less authoritative. Paynich (2009: 11) refers to these characteristics as "behavioural measures" in her study that was carried out in Massachusetts, USA.

II. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND ON POLICE EDUCATION

In the nineteenth century, a police officer getting any kind of formal education or training was an afterthought (Jaremko and Walker, 1978: 39). August Vollmer is recognized as the "father of modern law enforcement" and is credited with establishing the field's professionalism (O'Connor, 2019). When Vollmer was chosen as Berkeley's Marshal in 1905, many people did not want him to have that role. Officers were then notorious for their corruption and cruelty. Vollmer, a veteran of the Spanish-American War, thought that a police agency ought to function similarly to a military administration. Vollmer, who is credited with developing the "Code of Ethics" that police agencies employ today, insisted on the highest standards of honesty and fervently supported hiring law enforcement personnel with academic backgrounds.

In the early days of the law enforcement industry, it was not unusual for a police officer to be given a badge, a gun, and a club and told to "enforce the law" (Frost, 1959). Vollmer recognized this as a serious issue for law enforcement and set a change objective for it. Vollmer founded the first official academy for training police officers in 1908. As a result, other departments like Philadelphia, Detroit, and New York City soon followed suit (Roth, 2011). Vollmer contrasted a police officer to other occupations, claiming that they all require education and uphold a certain level of competency in their fields of specialization. When the UC Berkeley founded the first School of Criminology in 1916, it made history and allowed police officers from all across the West Coast to enroll in collegiate courses.

August Vollmer, the Berkeley, California, police chief in the early 1900s, was the driving force behind the movement for police personnel to receive more education. According to Carte (1973), Vollmer pushed for enhanced technical and intellectual skill utilisation among police officers in addition to a higher level of professionalism. When most police officers did not receive any kind of formal police training, he collaborated with the University of California, Berkeley, to create a police academy. Although the initial emphasis of these courses was on technical instruction for police officers, he also believed that established educational institutions should closely coordinate classroom instruction with on-the-job experience to train police students in the arts and sciences (Carte, 1973). In the 1930s, several top colleges launched alternative police-related bachelor programs in response to the popularity of the Berkeley courses (Crockett & Stinchcomb, 1968).

However, it wasn't until the late 1960s that a sizable number of police leaders and administrators in the United States started to discuss the advantages of higher education for police and the way in which higher education played a role in the development of police professionalism (Roberg and Bonn 2004). Since then, numerous studies on the effect of higher education on police attitudes and performance have been conducted, mostly in the United States. Although the bulk of reviews identified more positive consequences of university education, the enormous body of data demonstrates that higher education has both beneficial and bad effects on police.

Higher education can be perceived as a path to standardization, yet externally recognized credentials offer a chance to demonstrate transferrable skills and abilities, increasing job freedom (Jaschke & Neidhardt, 2007). It can also help officers grow personally and professionally by improving self-esteem and job motivation and giving them a sense that their knowledge and talents are recognized (Hallenberg, 2012). Importantly, HE promotes parity with other professions while also fostering increased performance and public perception (Hallenberg, 2012). Officers with HE backgrounds have been found to have an advantage in that they have a broader awareness of policing concerns as well as a variety of transferrable abilities (Hallenberg, 2012; Werth, 2011). Both the idea of it and the concern about it are not new.

After all, academic training is regarded as a vital aspect of professions, thought required due to the complexity of the task, the position of authority and responsibility held by professions, and the assurance of competence that educational credentials provide. A profession is defined and given legitimacy by its possession and control over the methods and technologies that flow from it (Abbott, 1988), which also reinforces its institutional control and cognitive hegemony (Ericson and Haggerty, 1997). Therefore, the process of professionalizing the police through academic education works to redefine and relegitimize the police, and it may even be done so on purpose. Survival is the name of the game in the "competitive system of professions"

(Abbott, 1988), in the more discerning market, and in the evolving society that puts more demands on the police while also publicly doubting its capacity and means to satisfy them. The police's status with the public, other professions, and the government is improved (social capital), which makes it easier to secure pay and resources (economic capital), and it gives them a much-needed advantage in "conflicts over competence" that they may find themselves involved in (Hallenberg, 2012).

The perception is that academia is more concerned with theory, research, and information analysis, as well as extending perspectives. Academic research typically involves long-term objectives and takes a while to deliver results, which is acknowledged and virtually expected. Even clearly career-oriented directly vocational courses are driven considerably more by academic and personal motivation than by meticulous scoping and needs analysis. Although academia is a place of formal education, it also emphasizes innovation, independence, and freedom of thinking (Henkel, 2000). On the other hand, police value practical knowledge and experience over theoretical understanding. They place more emphasis on management of practical difficulties and decision-making (Reiner, 2010). The 'emergency service' nature of much law enforcement, the need to prioritize urgent issues, and the amount of time leaders must devote to administrative, organizational, and political concerns all contribute to the lack of long-term management commitment to knowledge development through research (Goldstein, 2003). While academics are accustomed to unlimited experimentation and the possibility of both positive and negative outcomes, policing, which is governed by the law and public expectations, rarely permits this kind of risk-taking (ibid). The training is needs-driven and tailored to the organization's requirements. Although training has become more formalized in recent years, most learning still occurs informally through socialization processes.

The 'policing family' collective ethos, which values devotion to the organization, is the foundation of the occupational culture. Of course, the description above is intentionally dichotomized and oversimplified; in reality, these organizational and cultural traits are more ambiguous and fluid, especially in light of the current financial and political constraints on both the police and HE. Nevertheless, it serves to highlight the apparent (but possibly false) divide between academia and law enforcement.

Several leading researchers in the field have discovered that a university education has positive effects on senior officers' cynicism (Niederhoffer 1967), authoritarian behavior (Smith, Locke and Fenster 1970; Dalley 1975), citizen complaints (Cohen and Chaiken 1972; Lersch and Kunzman 2001), dogmatism (Cohen and Chaiken 1972; Lersch and Kunzman 2001), and self-esteem (Guller 1972). Fewer incidents of discretionary arrests (Finkenauer 1975), greater open-mindedness (Parker 1976), better performance ratings (Cascio 1977), better administrative skills (Wycoff and Susmilch, 1979), better performance in police academy

training (Lester 1983), and better informed practice and use of critical thinking in performing duties (Carter, Sapp and Stevens, 1989) are some of the improvements that have been made, more flexible problem-solving and improved decision-making (Carter and Sapp 1990), more value placed on moral behavior (Shernock, 1992) lower levels of use of force (Terrill and Mastroski, 2002) and a rise in initiative and leadership positions. Since measuring individual performance is frequently challenging, research on the effects of university education has focused more on police attitudes (Reiner 1998). Police organizations are diverse, subject to change over time, and can have disputed objectives. Performance metrics are therefore not universal and can differ amongst organizations (Roberg and Bonn 2004).

However, not all studies into the effects of a university degree on police has produced favorable results. A few unfavorable effects of a university education have been identified, such as lower levels of respect for the public (Shernock 1992), higher cynicism scores for junior officers, and higher attrition rates for police with higher degrees (Trojanowicz and Nicholson, 1976). There are still some unfavorable findings from important academics, despite the fact that the bulk of data about the influence of higher education are positive.

➤ *Police Education*

The education and training of police officers is important in ensuring that they have the information base, skills, attitudes, and values necessary to carry out their tasks in a way that is professional and consistent with the objectives of a democratic society. Police officers learn in a variety of non-formal and informal learning environments in addition to formal learning environments like classrooms and scenario-based training rooms (see "(Non-) Learning to police"). These environments exist outside of the explicit curriculum of police education and training institutions. In order to make sure that what is learned is what is required, the "police system," with all of its structures and frameworks, as well as its persons (such as police trainers, management, and supporting staff), shares both the power and responsibility. But as recent discussions regarding police professionalization and reform—which were partly inspired by George Floyd's passing—indicate (Boxer et al., 2021), there is much to be learned by putting a scientific lens on police education and training. Through scientific observation and re-evaluation, one leverage point of the complex system that frequently results in unfavourable consequences in interactions between police and citizens is addressed.

The influence of academic police education on police professional identities and the overall organizational culture of the police has received very little research thus far (Heslop, 2011). But via the process of socialization, professional communities like higher education and law enforcement have a significant impact on identity building. Institutions use expert knowledge systems to define and validate identities by offering means to interpret the social environment and an individual's position within it. It is true

that entering the cultural landscapes of higher education or law enforcement can be seen as a transforming event that necessitates a renegotiation of one's self-identity.

However, why are the police using Higher Education? Externally recognized credentials offer a mechanism to demonstrate transferable abilities and competencies, increasing career freedom (Hallenberg and cockcroft, 2012). Higher education can be considered as a path to standardization. Additionally, it can help officers grow personally and professionally by improving self-esteem and job motivation and giving them a sense that their knowledge and talents are respected. It is crucial that HE promotes parity with other professions and results in enhanced performance and public perception (Hallenberg, 2012). Officers with HE backgrounds have been found to benefit from a broader grasp of policing concerns as well as a variety of transferrable abilities (Roberg & Bonn, 2004).

Academic education also has the ability to aid in the process of professionalizing the police. Its importance is not new, and neither is the notion that it may be solved by enhancing training and education (Greenhill, 1981). Because of the complexity of the task, the position of authority and responsibility that professions have, and the assurance of competence that educational credentials provide, academic education is regarded as an essential component of professions. A profession is defined and given legitimacy when it has access to abstract knowledge, the methods and tools that come from it, and it also increases its institutional control and cognitive hegemony (Abbott, 1988). Therefore, the process of professionalizing the police through academic education works to redefine and re-legitimize the police, and it may even be done so on purpose. Survival is the name of the game in the "competitive system of professions" (Abbott, 1988), in the more discerning market, and in the evolving society that puts more demands on the police while also publicly doubting its capacity and means to satisfy them.

The police's status with the public, other professions, and the government is improved (social capital), which makes it easier to secure pay and resources (economic capital), and it gives them a much-needed advantage in "conflicts over competence" that they may find themselves involved in (Hallenberg, 2012). In contrast, police value practical knowledge over theoretical understanding. They are more focused on making decisions and handling practical concerns (Reiner, 2010). The 'emergency service' nature of much law enforcement, the need to prioritize urgent issues, and the amount of time that leaders must devote to administrative, organizational, and political concerns all account for the lack of long-term management commitment to knowledge development through research (Goldstein, 2003). Academics are accustomed to free experimentation and the possibility of both positive and negative outcomes, while policing, which is governed by the law and public expectations, can rarely afford this kind of risk-taking (ibid). In order to meet the needs of the organization, the training is needs-driven. Even though training has become more formalized over the past few

decades, a lot of learning still happens informally through socialization processes. The 'policing family' collective philosophy, which places a premium on organization loyalty, is at the heart of the workplace culture.

➤ *The Impact of Education and Training on Law Enforcement*

Regardless of the role one has in a law enforcement agency, education and training appear to be necessary (Timm and Christian 1991). Both have significant contributions to make to the legal system. Many of the duties that an officer is expected to execute are covered in training with clear instructions. As a result, even in emergency situations, trained cops frequently react consistently and reflexively while employing tried-and-true methods. In contrast, education aids in preparing officers to solve issues on their own and interact and communicate with others in a productive manner.

Various degrees of education and training may be necessary for different law enforcement positions, but both are required for every post. For instance, law enforcement personnel frequently interact with individuals from a variety of backgrounds, exercise significant discretion in many crucial circumstances (such as deciding whether or not to make an arrest, whether or not to fire a weapon, whether or not to evacuate a location in an emergency situation, and so forth), and are required to write incident reports. Only after acquiring a few fundamental decision-making and evaluation abilities that are often taught through various educational programs will one be able to complete these jobs with success. In addition, officers require practical instruction in a variety of physical skills connected to their jobs (such as making arrests, using firearms, operating machinery, and responding to emergencies).

Even though they rely more on knowledge and mental skills that are often learned and/or developed through formal education to accomplish most of their responsibilities, middle- and top-level administration personnel still need practical training in several areas. For instance, middle and senior police executives frequently require training in computer usage, the use of new software (such as crime mapping software) and other technologies that they will need personally, how to follow reporting procedures, and various other necessities that will enable them to complete the tasks for which they are accountable. Executives in law enforcement may also take part in training programs to become familiar with fresh evaluation tools and academic discoveries.

III. THE IMPORTANCE OF COLLEGE EDUCATION

In sum, advocates for higher educational standards for policing believe that increased education will in some way improve the performance and attitudes of officers. Education is supposed to add a humanistic element (i.e. a concern for human welfare) to policing (Roberg & Bonn, 2004) that makes officers “appreciate the role of police in a democratic society” and “be more tolerant of people different from

themselves” (Worden, 1990: 566). In particular, educated officers are expected to have a much stronger relationship with the community they serve (Carter & Sapp, 1990). It seems likely that more humanistic police officers would be less likely to hold attitudes supportive of abuse of authority. These intuitive arguments provided by policing scholars seem to be in line with the empirical research on college education and moral reasoning reviewed above.

➤ *Benefits of Education for Police Officers*

Wimhurst and Ransley (2007: 108) assert that higher education is seen as a means of reforming police organizations. The recruitment of police officers as well as their operational effectiveness and personal wellbeing are all thought to be enhanced by higher education (Wimhurst & Ransley, 2007: 108). Police officers are motivated by a variety of incentives to pursue higher education using their own free time and limited financial means. According to Jones, and Lister (2015: 5), there are four primary factors that encourage police officials to continue their education. Jones (2016) discovered that the primary driving forces were a desire to "remedy personal regrets" for not going to school before joining the police, to develop into a "well-rounded police officer," to increase opportunities for promotion and career development, as well as to get ready for a second career after active duty. Promotion was the main driver for pursuing further education, according to Buckley, McGinnis, and Petrunik (1993: 17).

Police officers perform better overall at their jobs when they have more education. Higher education is thought to enhance police officials' ability to do their jobs in a variety of ways, according to Paynich (2009: 11) and Telep (2011: 394). Higher education is thought to hone police officers' problem-solving abilities and offer creative solutions to issues instead of resorting to legal action. (Bruns, 2010: 99). Police officers who have more education "rated themselves significantly higher on several performance categories," according to Kakar (1998: 639).

To be effective at their jobs, police officers need to be capable of critical thinking and problem-solving as well as effective communication and legal knowledge (Birzer and Tannehill, 2001). Due to the improvement of critical thinking abilities brought on by college experience, higher education may have some advantages in this regard (Terenzini, 1993). Additionally, when working in the same position, people with college degrees perform better than those with only a high school diploma (Pascarella and Terenzini, 2005).

Higher education boosts police officers' professionalism, according to studies looking into its influence on the legal system. Higher education has several advantages, and police personnel in particular benefit from its benefits of creativity and critical thinking (Paterson, 2011). This is clear from the way officers with more education handle situations where using force—physical, chemical, or lethal—may be necessary. According to Rydberg (2010), an officer with higher education is much less likely to use force than an officer without a college

degree. Reduced substantiated internal affairs complaints are a result of higher education levels (Hoptay, 2007). Bachelor's degree holders in law enforcement are less likely to put up with abuses of power (Telep, 2011). All of these indications point to the professional development of police personnel through higher education.

A college education enhances a wide range of abilities, including communication, critical thinking, judgement, and reasoning, which helps college graduates make the necessary changes in their lives (Pascarella and Terenzizi, 1995). Individuals who start their college careers at a two-year university still receive this benefit. Evidence reveals that the difference between two- and four-year college degrees in terms of how well students improve their cognitive abilities, critical thinking, and reasoning is, at best, negligible (Bohr et al., 1994).

Higher educated police officers were shown to be more adept at using technology effectively and drafting effective reports (Gardiner, 2015: 655). Report writing is crucial and relevant to criminal prosecution and procedural issues (Gardiner, 2015: 655). Higher education gives police officers the abilities to carry out their duties more effectively and to make ongoing judgments about policing without constant supervision or with little oversight, claim Carter and Sapp (1990: 62). Higher-educated police officers are "excellent employees who use less sick time, are involved in fewer traffic collisions, are disciplined less often, and receive more commendations," according to Bostrom (2005: 7). Kakar (1998: 642) discovered that police officers' educational backgrounds had no discernible influence on whether they were given praise or discipline. Higher-educated police officers are more adaptable to change (Kakar, 1998: 634).

Police officers that have completed higher education programs have the critical thinking abilities that are essential for carrying out their tasks. Critical thinking abilities give police officers the chance to, among other things, identify and challenge untested beliefs as well as establish methods and means to solve challenges faced by communities, according to Vickers (2000: 512) as well as Lee and Punch (2004: 245). In order to meet the demands connected with policing, it lays the groundwork for "critical, enquiring, and challenging minds" (Lee & Punch, 2004: 248). Additionally, it gives receivers a better understanding of "police policy and strategy" (Jones, 2016: 6).

Promotion opportunities within the police hierarchy are increased by tertiary education. When Kordaczuk-Was and Sosnowski (2011: 319) examined the role of self-education in Polish law enforcement organizations, they discovered that it was marked by a high degree of commitment and effort, the acquisition of which led to an improvement in professional qualification and the performance of more significant duties. This consequently has the ability to have an impact on achieving a higher rank within the police rank system (Kordaczuk-Was & Sosnowski, 2011: 319). In order to increase their eligibility for promotion within their organizations or to boost their competitiveness when

applying for police executive posts, police supervisors and commanding officers pay for their own tuition (Cordner & Shain, 2011: 282). According to Buker (2010: 61), the TNP's promotion policy provides for the appointment of individuals with such skills to supervisory posts without having any experience as operational police officers, hence recognizing higher education.

A factor in complaints made against police organizations is higher education. Telep, (2011) discovered that cops without college degrees were engaged in 75% of disciplinary cases in Florida that resulted from public complaints. The most persistent formal complaints were made against police officers who did not hold a college degree (Manis et al., 2008: 516). Higher education is primarily seen by Australian authorities as a way to combat police "corruption and serious misconduct" (Cox, et al 2011: 14). Cohen and Chaiken also discovered fewer complaints against educated police officers (Paynich, 2009: 12). Higher educated police personnel are less likely to be involved in accidents that may have been avoided (Gardiner, 2015: 650).

Higher educated police officers are less likely to use physical force while carrying out their jobs. College-educated police officers, in Kakar's estimation (1998:639), rely more on the effectiveness of "mediation and conflict resolution techniques" than on the use of physical force. Rydberg and Terrill's (2010: 107) findings showing cops exposed to college education were less likely to use force than their non-college educated counterparts lend credence to this viewpoint. Chapman (2012: 434) discovered that trained police officers made arrests with "less force and lower levels of force". However, Kakar, 1998: 635, maintains that this category of police officials is less likely to be assault victims. Paynich, (2009), contends that police officials with higher education are less inclined to protect themselves should they be confronted by danger as compared to their less educated peers. Telep (2011: 400) discovered that police officers with college degrees were more likely to obey the law's limitations on the use of force. Higher education is associated with community tolerance and sensitivity to diversity. Police officers with higher education were shown to be more adaptable in dealing with complicated issues as well as in their relationships with clients from various contexts, according to Carter and Sapp (1990: 62). The "behaviour and attitude" of police officers in their encounters with persons of other races and minorities is seen to be shaped by higher education.

The life and performance of a police officer have been demonstrated to directly and significantly correlate with college education in numerous studies. The police' activities and contacts with the public are primarily the focus of these consequences. Many of these impacts are described by Roberg and Bonn (2004), including declines in authoritarianism, improvements in discretionary use, improved acculturation to the communities that the officers serve, and an increase in community policing. As discussed before, police officers are known for being harsh and having a very authoritarian demeanor while interacting with the populace they are sworn to protect. Smith, Locke, and

Walker (1967) conducted a study to see whether a college education would lessen this attitude with the aim of reaching conclusions regarding the authoritarian views seen in many police officers and the influence that education may have on those attitudes. Smith, Locke, and Walker showed that while controlling for numerous variables, cops who are drawn to and enroll in college "are significantly less authoritarian than police who are not impelled to attend college"—supporting the notion. Smith, Locke, and Walker's (1968) discovery that "the freshman police officer college students tend to be less authoritarian than the freshmen students who are not police officers" (pp. 442-443) led to additional investigation of this topic. As a result, police officers with college degrees were generally rated as being less authoritarian than the typical college student.

Germann, (1967) argued in favour of raising the bar for police officers' college degrees. Germann held the opinion that a professional police officer was one who had received the education and training that a college education offers as opposed to an officer who had received merely practical training. According to Germann, "he must use the greatest diplomacy and tact if he is to maintain the confidence of the populace. No officer with inadequate education can handle the demands of the job (p. 604). Many argued that police officers should be held to the same standards as other public servants as a result of this and the Federal police personnel are required to have a college degree both then and now. Additionally, Germann said that hiring someone with "broad education" would "...provide professional preparation" for the officer to fit into their department. By hiring people from a variety of backgrounds, one may find those who are able to learn the duties of a police officer and who have already had professional development training, which was thought to assist the department become more professional. This has been hotly contested in the literature, with several research (Harris, 1949; Loughry & Freise Jr. 1969) supporting Germann's position.

Green and Linsdell (2010) favor higher education levels for the sake of education rather than attempting to train officers in particular fields. This means that Green and Linsdell support higher education in general rather than promoting a degree specifically for police officers. Higher education, in their opinion, improves research, analytical, and critical thinking abilities (p. 156). These are undoubtedly some of the most crucial abilities that police officers employ to carry out their daily tasks. Others who agree that the more educated officer is more equipped for the job than the less educated officers who receive merely police school training (Hallenberg & Cokroft, 2012) have confirmed these findings.

The way that police officers are viewed by both their fellow officers and the general public is another considered advantage of higher education for police officers. This holds true for their opinions on their work, their level of job satisfaction, and the value of higher education in general. Most studies have found little to no association between greater education and job happiness or job satisfaction and overall job opinion. This topic will be covered in more detail

in a later chapter of this work. When comparing these officers to those with only a high school diploma, Telep (2008) found that college experience of any level "had a positive impact on attitudes [regarding use of force]" (p. 72). This was true for all evaluated educational levels, albeit it was not determined to be statistically significant at the associate's level to the same extent as it was at the other levels. Additionally, it was determined that the data were not statistically significant enough to fully support the theory, but they were still enough to be measured. This, according to the author, may be because those who went to "some college" were enrolled in 4-year programs. Additionally, Telep discovered that, in comparison to officers without a college education, officers who had a bachelor's degree prior to employment did not affect their opinions toward the abuse of authority. Regarding the subject at issue, this stands in stark contrast to the idea that rising educational levels will reduce citizen complaints. The idea of raising educational standards would be refuted by the fact that the majority of citizen complaints include the use of force and/or misuse of authority, as common experience teaches the typical person.

Bruns and Magnan (2014) discovered that while many of the middle level executives and policemen within the surveyed police organizations believed that higher education was crucial, this was not always the case. This indicates that top leadership thought education was crucial for the organization and the future of policing, while individual police officers' views on the advantages of a college degree for the workplace varied. Many people believed that education was not important for job success, while others thought it was, and yet others thought that more education wasn't harmful either. This demonstrates the diversity of views among police officers themselves regarding the value of higher education, both before and after joining the force. While relatively few police groups demanded more than a high school graduation, Edwards (2017) discovered that many police officers opted to enroll in college courses of their own choosing, both before and while serving. Edwards also found that educational level played an important role in the attitudes held by police officers towards higher education, causing many to advocate for the increasing of educational requirements for police officers. These results remained consistent when compared to a variety of factors including gender, age, and specific agency police officers were employed at; with none of these factors affecting the aforementioned attitudes.

These findings, which were discovered among police officers themselves, support the idea that a greater level of education could benefit officers and reduce citizen complaints. They need careful consideration. It should be highlighted that the results only applied to officers with degrees that were comprehensive, as opposed to those who had little or no college education. The findings indicate that police officers with higher levels of degree completion believe that a higher education benefits their work as police officers. When analyzing Minnesota police officers' perceptions of higher education as a hiring requirement, Hilal and Zhao (2013) discovered comparable findings. Although Minnesota currently has the nations highest first

hire standards, according to Hilal and Zhao, a third of Minnesota officers believe they should be even higher (pg. 473).

This demonstrates that when it comes to police personnel, people appreciate better education. According to the study, 30% of officers said that a Bachelor's degree should be the minimum qualification, and more than 70% said that they would still have applied for the position if the requirement had already been a reality. Hilal and Zhao also discovered that lower level officers and not high level administrators were more likely to experience these emotions. When trying to determine the effects of educational level at the patrol officer level, this offers even stronger support for the beneficial benefit of higher education. High self-esteem, a decrease in complaints against the police, better decision-making, and a better understanding of the role and functions of the police are additional advantages of tertiary education for police officials (Decker & Huckabee, 2002: 793). College education "significantly" decreased the "likelihood" of the use of force in police confrontations with members of the community, according to Rydberg and Terrill (2010: 92) and Kakar (1998: 639). Higher education is linked to traits like the capacity to relate to the social, political, and historical aspects of everyday life, say Roberg and Bonn (2004). Higher education is crucial, according to Palmiotto (1999: 73) and Stanislas (2014: 60), in developing police officers' understanding of the social and cultural diversity of their constituents. Police officers with tertiary education, according to Sherwood and Jeffery, (2000: 196), want autonomy and more difficult jobs.

The degree of education and quality of training, according to Goldstein (in Kakar, 1998: 635) are the two factors that have the biggest impact on whether police officials succeed or fail in their jobs. According to Jaschke (2010: 302) and Scaramella et al. (2011: 94), police has gotten more complicated, necessitating a shift away from the conventional experience-based training and instruction toward a policing style that depends on science and research. Police officers increasingly need to have more than just physical stamina and common sense, as the nature of policing is changing (Kakar, 1998: 634).

Political leaders, however, are against the academically oriented approach to police because they worry about losing control of policing (Jaschke, 2010: 308). Researchers have also questioned the benefits of higher education for law enforcement professionals and for policing (Carlan, 2007: 609). According to Niederhoffer (1995: 11), detractors of higher education contend that hiring college graduates is a costly luxury that does not result in an effective overall performance and that less experienced police officers with higher qualifications are skeptical of efforts to professionalize police agencies. According to some, college education, especially in the field of criminal justice, has not done a good enough job of preparing students for the realities of law enforcement (Carlan, 2007: 609).

Higher education is not considered useful to policing by certain managers and supervisors in law enforcement organizations (Carlan, 2007: 609). The American Bar Association (ABA, in Palombo, 1995: 39) claims that some police managers even intimidate and constrain police personnel who attempt to use their newly gained abilities in their interactions with the community. Hawley (1998: 47), claim that police officers believe their agencies are unwilling to support their efforts to obtain higher degrees. According to Carter et al., (1989: 18), it is impractical to rely on universities to provide recruits, and college-educated graduates become bored and frustrated by irregular working hours, routine work, low salaries, and the autocratic management style used by police agencies. Additionally, Carter et al., 1989: 19) worries that police personnel with greater education will anticipate receiving preferential treatment and that they "cause animosity within the ranks."

Owen and Wagner discovered that criminal justice graduates in the USA tended to be more authoritarian than other graduates (Patterson, 2011: 289). Additionally, Worden (Chappell, & Lanza-Kaduce, 2010: 276) believes that higher education has either little or no impact on police. When compared to their counterparts without college degrees, police officers with higher degrees were shown to be more likely to defy authority and leave their jobs sooner (Bromley, 1999: 78).

When comparing police officers who attended college before joining the force to those who did not, (Decker & Huckabee, 2002: 793) found no discernible variations in views. Some researchers have also questioned the worth of higher education and the applicability of the courses taught, Bromley, (1999: 78). Higher education institutions are viewed negatively by those opposed to it because they prioritize making money over raising educational standards Paterson, (2011: 288). Due to the fact that curricula vary, the mere acquisition of a degree does not guarantee that the person is educated (Decker & Huckabee, 2002: 793). When they assert that, unlike teachers and nurses, police officers are appointed as constables even after failing or not completing a foundation degree in art, White and Heslop (2012: 343) demonstrate the lack of esteem for higher education.

Higher education is linked to unfavorable attitudes including work unhappiness and a high staff turnover rate. Because they were seen as having more job prospects, police officers with tertiary degrees were shown to be three times more likely to resign from the police agencies than their peers without a higher degree (Jones et al., 2005: 52). Employee expectations are frequently high in higher education, and if these expectations are not satisfied, they may cause irritation and unhappiness, which may cause turnover (Kakar, 1998: 634). Studies conducted by the Turkish National Police (TNP), the Minnesota Police Department, and the Queensland Police Service in Australia, Turkey, and the United States, however, revealed that police officers with degrees were generally happier with their salaries than their non-degreed counterparts (Jones et al., 2005: 59).

Pursuing university education is sometimes considered as a sign of disloyalty, whereas police personnel who have already graduated are seen as "lacking long-term commitment" to the police agency, according to Jones et al. (2005: 50) and Hunt and McCadden (in Tankebe, 2010: 76). According to Jones et al. (2005: 52), college-educated police officers' "low job satisfaction" might have a major detrimental effect on their commitment. According to Decker & Huckabee, (2002: 792), a lack of challenge may cause police personnel to get disillusioned and leave their jobs in large numbers. In India, it was discovered that police personnel with tertiary education had strict attitudes, were unconcerned with upholding the rights of the public, and did not confine themselves to the boundaries set by the law (Paterson, 2011: 291). It follows from the explanation above that obtaining a higher education or pursuing it is viewed negatively by the police.

Hanak, Hofinger, and Brodeur observe that police departments in nations like the Czech Republic, Greece, France, and Italy have already attained the stature of colleges (in Paterson, 2011: 290). For senior police officers, the German Police University offers a master's degree, and for intermediate managers, 17 other police academies offer bachelor's degrees (Jaschke, 2010: 305). To become a Commissioned Officer in Hungary, one must complete higher education, which is solely provided by the National University of Public Service (Sandor, 2014: 182-183). Focusing on hiring college graduates for the police was suggested by the relevant ministries and the National Development and Reform Commission of China (Tingyou, 2014: 203). The enhancement of higher education in the police is a goal of China's Chinese People's Public Security University (Tingyou, 2014: 203). Although neither a degree nor a diploma is a requirement for employment, Canadian police organizations prefer that new hires have one (Wyatt & Bell, 2014: 74).

A 2008 study in Minnesota, USA, found that fewer officers supported requiring at least a four-year degree to earn the license needed to work as a police officer (Hilal & Erickson, 2010: 19). A bachelor's degree or greater certification should be required for supervisors, according to more officers (Hilal & Erickson, 2010: 20). According to Woods (in Palombo, 1995: 39), the majority of police administrators have long supported requiring an advanced degree for higher-ranking officers and a college degree for recruits. It's interesting to note that approximately half of Minnesota's police officers have a bachelor's degree or higher, making them better educated than the people they serve (Hilal & Erickson, 2010: 19). In order to have enough applicants and prevent claims of discrimination against minority groups, the New York Police Department (NYPD) and the Portland Police Bureau (PPB) in the USA have relaxed the higher education requirement (Dantzker, 2003: 299). In order to implement the higher education requirement, the New Jersey State Police in the USA made an effort to find a sufficient number of recruits from minority groups (Dantzker, 2003: 299).

IV. COLLEGE LEARNING AND LAW ENFORCEMENT

Since almost a century ago, academics have researched how education affects police work and performance (Finckenauer, 2005). The pattern was accelerating. Higher education seemed like a decent notion for the police; many people thought that college would improve officers' performance; it felt like a logical evolutionary step for a profession in its infancy. We find reasons why police officers should be encouraged to get a college degree for the following causes as researchers who focus on crime and punishment:

➤ *Behaviours Related to Morality:*

Earning a college degree is also connected to moral convictions and moral behaviour. College has a net positive effect on moral reasoning, according to Pascarella and Terenzini's 2005 analysis. According to Kohlberg (1981, 1984), principled moral thinking is a three-level process. People progress from being highly egocentric and pre-conventional (Level I) to conventional (Level II) and concerned with obeying the rules to avoid punishment (Level III) to post-conventional (Level III) and concerned with more universal concepts of morality. In the post-conventional state, people try to respect other people's rights and practice moral reasoning from a position of principle. Pascarella and Terenzini (2005) found that senior undergraduate students exhibit a degree of principled moral reasoning that is 0.77 standard deviations (28 percentile points) greater than freshmen students in their synthesis of the research from the 1990s. They come to the conclusion that this transition from traditional moral reasoning to principled moral reasoning occurs throughout college (Trevino, 1992).

Principled moral reasoning has also been associated favorably with moral behaviors and acts in domains like business ethics (Arnold & Poneman, 1991), resistance to cheating, and, critically for law enforcement, reporting corruption. Although there are other links between principled moral reasoning and principled moral action, these relationships suggest that the change brought about by a college degree should result in more moral behaviour.

➤ *Less Likely to use Violence:*

According to research, cops with a college education tend to receive fewer complaints from the public. Additionally, they are less likely to use force and terminated for misconduct. Officers who have completed their college education are roughly 40% less likely to use force. The term "use of force" refers to a variety of behaviours, including verbal threats to use force and actual use of force that may result in physical harm.

Officers with college degrees are also less likely to discharge their weapons. According to a study of officer-involved shootings from 1990 to 2004, police officers with a college education were about 30% less likely to use deadly force while on the job. Additionally, a research discovered that police departments that required officers to have at least

a two-year degree had a lower likelihood of officers being assaulted by civilians than departments that did not. According to studies, only approximately 5% of police officers are responsible for the majority of citizen complaints, and officers with only a two-year degree are only about half as likely to belong to this group. Researchers also discovered that police with at least a two-year degree had a 40% lower risk of losing their positions due to misconduct.

➤ *More Problem-Oriented:*

In order to improve police-community relations and respond more effectively to crime and other social problems, the 2015 task force suggested community- and problem-oriented policing tactics. A proactive approach to identifying crime issues in communities is problem-oriented policing. In accordance with the plan, police must also identify the root causes of crime, formulate effective countermeasures, and evaluate the effectiveness of such countermeasures. Similar to this, community-oriented police places a strong emphasis on establishing connections with residents in order to recognize and address local crime issues. People are happier with how police serve their community and perceive them as more legitimate when police departments employ community-policing tactics, according to research. Problem-solving and creative thinking are necessary for community policing and problem-focused policing; these are abilities that college helps students acquire.

Future police officers can hone their civic involvement abilities through options like internships and service learning in college. Additionally, it gives them a chance to get to know the neighborhoods they would be policing. Eighty percent of students who took part in a criminal justice service-learning course that involved working with local youth reported a shift away from presuming that all of them would be criminals and toward a better understanding of them as unique people with goals and potential, some of which were similar to the students' own aspirations. Nearly 90% claimed to have gained a better understanding of the community, which they felt would be useful for their future work in criminal justice. A bachelor's degree considerably boosts dedication to community policing among street-level police who contact with the public the most. Instead than only responding to calls for service, these officers frequently work more proactively with community members to solve difficulties and avoid crises.

➤ *Enables Officers to Better Relate to the Community:*

The technical training that cops receive in the school or on the job is improved by higher education, according to research. For instance, as college students, future or present police officers take part in internships, volunteer work, or international studies. These things have all been found to improve moral reasoning, diversity acceptance, and critical thinking. College also increases one's awareness of other cultures. All of these abilities are necessary for effective police work when combined. Additionally, studies have revealed that police personnel themselves appreciate a college education. They claim that a college education enhances a person's communication skills, openness to

diversity, knowledge of the law and the judicial system, among other things. According to a survey, criminal justice graduates who worked as police officers claimed their training gave them administrative abilities.

➤ *Helps Officers Identify Best Practices:*

College education improves officers' ability to recognize reliable data and scientific evidence. In turn, this makes it easier for them to more thoroughly and frequently assess the policies and procedures set by their departments. De-escalation strategies, for instance, are frequently used by departments to lessen the need for force. Evaluating an approach's impact is a crucial stage in determining whether it is succeeding in attaining its intended purpose. Officers are better equipped to make changes to their department's rules if they comprehend scientific procedures as they are taught in college.

➤ *Builds Better Leaders:*

Effective police reform necessitates transformational leadership. Graduate degrees and higher education can help criminal justice professionals advance in the ranks and develop their leadership potential. Compared to officers without a college education, police officers with at least some college experience are more focused on promotions and anticipate retiring at a higher position. The fact that police administrators, especially police chiefs, are more likely to have undergraduate and graduate degrees shouldn't come as a surprise. Graduate-level leaders are twice as likely to be familiar with the concept of evidence-based policing, which makes use of research to inform efficient policy and practice.

The future of both police reform and higher education is in jeopardy. Law enforcement personnel with more education will be more qualified to oversee urgently required reform initiatives. Incentives like the Nebraska Law Enforcement Education Act, which permits a partial tuition waiver, the Quinn Bill in Massachusetts, which offers scaled bonuses depending on the degree an officer holds, or tuition reimbursement scholarships like those provided by the Fraternal Order of Police are just a few examples of what state and local agencies and governments can do more to encourage officers to pursue a college degree. The skills that officers need to help rebuild trust between our communities and those who are sworn to protect and serve can be learned in colleges and universities.

➤ *Police Performance:*

In accordance with several studies, police officers who have more education tend to make more arrests (Bozza, 1973). Bozza's study found that younger officers with higher education levels made more arrests than older officers with lower education levels. He arrived at this conclusion by looking at data from a California police department. Similar to this, Glasgow, Green, and Knowles (1973) bolster this assertion with research demonstrating a connection between a police officer's educational background and the number of arrests made. Arrest rates may not be a reliable predictor of effective job performance in police agencies that value and implement a community policing approach in their

department. Other police agencies might view citizen complaints as a more accurate indicator of personnel performance. For instance, Cohen and Chaiken (1972) discovered that education level is the most effective predictor of complaints from civilians in a study of New York City police officers. There is evidence to support the idea that police personnel with more education are less likely to face citizen complaints (Paynich, 2009). Law enforcement employees' performance may be evaluated based on a variety of criteria, such as citizen complaints, the ability to resolve conflicts without constantly making arrests, and improved public relations. Additionally, Manis (2007) discovered that as compared to police officers with merely a high school degree, the more educated a police officer is, the less probable it is that complaints will be made against him or her.

In conclusion, it is suggested that an officer with a college education is more knowledgeable about civil rights concerns from a legal, social, historical, and political standpoint. Additionally, because these officers have a broader perspective on policing duties and a stronger professional ethos, their actions and judgments are more likely to be guided by conscience and principles, which lowers the possibility of making bad choices. The logical inference is that the college-educated officer would be less likely to put the department in a liability situation if these arguments are true (Carter & Sapp, 1989: 162).

V. COLLEGE LEARNING AND PROMOTIONAL ASPIRATIONS

Researchers have known for a long time that the motivation for police officers to pursue a college degree is frequently a desire for professional promotion (Buckley, McGinnis, & Petrunik, 1993). Therefore, it is surprising that not much study has been done on the connection between higher education and career aspirations (Albarano, 2015). According to the few studies that have been conducted, officers with higher levels of education are more likely to desire promotions than those without college degrees (Gau, Terrill, & Paoline, 2013). Their aspirations for advancement, motivated by ambition and self-assurance in their policing skills, frequently coincide with a proactive enforcement approach, producing a more spirited brand of policing (Bozza, 1973). College-educated police are more likely to exhibit harsh or unfair treatment of residents when they are not able to achieve their professional goals (Ercikti, Vito, Walsh, & Higgins, 2011).

Even less is known about the impact of promotional aspirations on policing behaviors if research on the impact of higher education on officers' promotional aspirations is limited. But it is evident that desire for advancement is a major factor in determining police officers' enforcement priorities (Gau et al., 2013). In other words, police officers act appropriately because they are aware of what it takes to advance. College education is not a requirement for promotion, according to some academics (Baro & Burlingame, 1999), and conventional productivity indicators like traffic stops, searches, and arrests are given more

weight in such decisions (Paoline, 2001). Officers with college degrees may be more ambitious than their less educated counterparts, which makes them more dedicated to traditional promotion standards and zealous law enforcement (Gau et al., 2013). According to Paoline & Terrill's 2005 research, cops with more education tended to use harsher enforcement tactics, operate with a higher level of selectivity, distrust of the public, and hostility toward monitoring.

VI. FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

➤ *Progress Made So Far*

- One of the key goals of first police training should be to shift the emphasis away from intense physical training and toward the development of knowledge, skills, attitudes, alongside the empathy, compassion, and common sense that British police officers already possess, and behaviours. An individual officer's personal and professional growth will continually place ethics at the forefront of their study and preparation for a professional career, supporting educational programs. Police practice will be able to provide consideration of human rights and respect for equality priority in order to maintain the pride for democracy and the rule of law in the diverse British society. It is common knowledge that for police officers to efficiently carry out their demanding duties and defend the law, they must be in good physical and mental condition. They must learn first aid, law, and drills, but the PEQF will place less of an emphasis on parades and drills with a vaguely military feel. Instead, they will undergo necessary Officer Safety Training (OST) before they are put into use.
- On a purpose-built campus with technology-enhanced master classrooms, small classrooms for seminars and group discussions, and an assessment center with the necessary resources for student officers who need extra assistance, the police forces should offer residential housing for the aspiring officers. It is essential to have the resources for physical training, arm training, safety training, a gym, a sports facility, and a hydra simulation suit in order to promote immersive learning. Students who live on the campus of the HEI may have time and space for safe learning in addition to their present access to the library and online resources.
- If the PEQF is successfully implemented, society will be able to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for peace and prosperity through reasonable policing by graduate officers who will be able to use their cognitive, affective, and psychomotor skills to make informed decisions. This will help society meet the demands of the twenty-first century. The UK has historically been at the forefront of the development of professional policing, and if the academic professional qualification programs based on the PEQF are successful (as the first PCDA cohort is anticipated to be qualified in 2021 and the first Pre-Join Degree students will be graduated in 2022), this model of ideal police education will be adopted by other nations, particularly in those

looking for effective police reform to address the crises of lethal violence and drug trafficking. Although the lack of legitimacy of the police has been attributed to the police occupational culture for many years, this new policing model will bring about a dramatic change in that culture. Police work is referred to as a performing art and the paradigm shift as a reforming process by Savage (2007).

- The NSW Police Force (NSWPF) has created a unique program in collaboration with Charles Sturt University (CSU), where prospective candidates must first complete the University Certificate in Workforce Essentials (UCWE), a foundation-level program, before they can be offered a position as a police recruit and enrol in the program. The NSW Police Academy and CSU's School of Policing Studies jointly administer this course, which requires student officers to live at the Academy during the week (NSW Police, 2020). In addition, this two-year program involves a field observation placement in Year 1 after attestation, after which the students will continue their studies in Year 2 as probationary constables. The successful completion of Year 2 will, however, be a requirement for their employment as police constables (Green, Woolston, 2014).
- The Bangladesh Police Academy, Sardah, which was founded in 1912 in Bengal under British rule, continues to provide fully residential basic police training (Bangladesh Police, 2020). A greater emphasis is placed on physical training, including early morning exercise, morning parades, afternoon parades, and horse training (for probationer Assistant Superintendents who join through the national civil service). However, since 2008, after successfully completing this police-led training, probationary Assistant Superintendents of Police have been awarded a Masters of Police Science degree from the University of Rajshahi. Due to persistent opposition from the civil bureaucracy and a lack of strong political will since the decision-makers want to maintain their tight control over the force, the UNDP-DFID-sponsored Police Reform Programme in Bangladesh failed to bring about a paradigm shift in police training and culture. Similar to this, many police agencies both in developed and developing nations have their own police academies and training facilities. For example, the Louisiana State Police Training Academy in the United States has a residential academy in Baton Rouge and a sizable training facility that includes the Joint Emergency Services Training Center (Louisiana State Police, 2016). The physical learning environment is equally important for a positive learning experience. In fact, it is argued that uniformed PCDA and DHEP students' inability to find adequately furnished on-campus housing alternatives may harm their academic performance and sense of community as members of a disciplined force. The other professional degrees that institutions provide could teach us more in this area, and they could be adjusted for these programs.

➤ *Leadership Development*

One of the top concerns for global policing in the twenty-first century is the development of police leadership (Hoggett, Redford, Toher, White, 2019). In the near future, 43 forces in England and Wales will be able to promote the apprentice-turned-graduates from the PCDA program, officers with a graduate diploma from the DHEP, and officers who graduated from policing. Despite the fact that there are five ways to enter the police force—constable, police staff, Fast Track to inspector, Direct Entry at superintendent, and Direct Entry at chief constable (for qualified overseas chief officers)—the majority of senior officers start out as constables and advance through the ranks the conventional way. Future leaders will undoubtedly be developed through the Fast Track program, which is available to both fresh recruits and seasoned police, as well as Police Now, which oversees the National Graduate Leadership Programme and the National Detective Programme.

An ethically and economically varied society requires a "diverse student body," but it's also about learning values and attitudes, which are necessary qualities for leadership. Similar to this, according to Bok (2010:19), "our institutions are now the leading sources of all three of the most crucial ingredients for progress and prosperity in modern societies: new discoveries, expert knowledge, and highly trained people." He continues, "Universities are the fundamental institutions for developing leaders across society. Our institutions will educate practically every top corporate executive as well as every politician, government official, judge, doctor, and clergyperson. Many times unobserved, but an increasing number of these leaders are going back to school in the middle of their careers to deepen their education.

The forces will therefore benefit from having more responsible police commanders who can provide variety of thought and viewpoint to policing as a result of higher education. They should take CPD courses throughout their careers to stay informed, get ready to lead the forces, establish credibility, and serve as role models for the rest of the world. To "Create a new model of leadership and management training and development which is accessible to all within policing," according to the College of Policing's Leadership Review (2015:31).

One of the cornerstones to an organization's efficiency, effectiveness, and success in managing people and attaining objectives is leadership. The police are allegedly a "totalizing institution" with a "chain of command," according to Bowling et al. (2019: 28). Therefore, it is crucial that the police forces develop future leaders who are qualified to command their particular units. (College of Policing, 2015: 6) claims that:

The ideal police commander "challenges themselves, and they adapt quickly, and is motivated by the core values of policing." An effective leader is one who empowers, believes in, and encourages each person to succeed among their peers, in their teams, and throughout their

organizations; one who manages the challenges posed by new criminal activity and issues with public safety; one who values diversity and difference; and one who readily accepts personal responsibility while maintaining the confidence of communities.

➤ *Pedagogical Aspects*

Police training has traditionally been centered on a top-down, instructor-led style of instruction that emphasizes the technical skills of a student officer (Paterson, 2015). These methods contrast with the learner-led participatory teaching and learning that is the norm in higher education, where success depends on the ability to think critically and creatively. However, research on the pedagogical effects of various educational and training pathways into policing is scant. In light of this, we want to see more in-depth conversation amongst academics and practitioners about the connection between the NPC and higher education abroad (Bowling, Reiner, Sheptycki, 2019).

In accordance to a survey of social work graduate students, classroom instruction did not effectively prepare them for practice in the field (Clapton, Cree, 2004). In the professional contexts, the police officers' learning must be followed by reflective thought and internal processing that links the experience with prior learning (Wilkinson, 2017). Effective learning is hindered by the inability to apply knowledge in a meaningful and relevant way. Practical examples aid students in comprehending and applying textbook concepts to actual circumstances, enhancing their learning experiences. Similar ideas that subject knowledge should not be disconnected from practical concerns were presented in *The Relation of Theory to Practice in Education* (Caskey 1979). Due to their lack of experiences, new students may find learning challenging in the early stages of academic police education programs. However, to help the trainees comprehend the settings and connect with the theories, instances from their earlier lives might be developed and provided through a virtual learning environment. Since student police officers who are too afraid to put their skills to the test will likely be anxious police officers, which is completely unanticipated, they should be given the chance to handle real-life situations.

VII. COMMUNICATION WITH OTHERS AND CRITICAL THINKING

Interpersonal communication abilities, along with critical thinking, are crucial components of police education as a professional course (Peach and Clare, 2017). Police officers are citizens in uniform, according to the nine Peelian principles of policing, and they cannot thrive without the community's support and endorsement (Neyroud, Loader, Brown, Muir, 2016). There should be a successful method for imparting interpersonal skills across the professional education program's curriculum in order to give student officers a solid basis and enable them to reduce some of the barriers separating the police force and the general public. New officers receive crucial foundational training through academic programs during their initial training because they must become proficient

communicators before performing tactical and legal tasks in real-world situations.

When the public and police work together to build secure, crime-free communities, effective policing results. Police officers must be well-prepared for this cooperation and exhibit both excellent technical and interpersonal skills. As a result, police forces, which are law enforcement organizations, must teach its personnel how to communicate and cooperate with the general people. Technical and people skills are helpful for officers to do their police work effectively in a professional atmosphere.

Police officers must continuously reflect on their knowledge and experience to successfully navigate the unique obstacles and critical discussions that are a part of their job. Making the officers critical reflective thinkers and the students reflect and write in their reflective journals during these work-based learning experiences is therefore a major goal of the PCDA and DHEP. For effective learning and skill development, the practice must be incorporated into degree programs, as suggested by Hornyak, Green, and Heppard (2007), who contend that people learn best from hands-on experience with guided reflection and analysis. The ideal student learning environment and the development of the information, attitudes, and abilities required for student officers to become fully qualified police constables are also vital.

A recent study (Cox and Kirby, 2018) found that university students majoring in police studies soon developed a police identity, which had an impact on their views and behavior. Police services must encourage and support their police officers in becoming reflective practitioners through critical thinking, and policing must be a reflective practice in the truest sense in order to realize the full potential of the PEQF (Wood, 2020). Only when recently created academic police studies programs are able to teach critical thinking and interpersonal communication skills will HEIs be able to offer drastically improved and well-equipped policing degrees for the better future.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This article gives readers a sense of the body of work that has already been written about the connection between higher education and police officers. In addition to ways unrelated to the subject at hand, this relationship has also been extensively explored in other ways. Although there isn't a clear consensus in the literature as a whole, many of the results support the idea that a college degree is good for police officers. Additionally, almost all of the negative findings were neutral, which means they did not necessarily refute but also did not support the idea that police personnel benefit from higher education.

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